

VULNERABILITY TO VIABILITY
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Small Indigenous Fisheries in the Ganga River Basin: Shifts Towards Viability from Vulnerabilities

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Abstract

Small Indigenous Fisheries in the Ganga River Basin form a crucial component of inland small-scale fisheries, sustaining livelihoods, nutrition, and cultural identity of local communities. However, hydrological alterations driven by climate change, river alteration, sediment imbalance, and pollution are disrupting the ecological conditions of the river. Despite growing evidence on nutritional and socio-economic importance of SIFs, the relationship between hydrological dynamics and SIF ecology remains poorly understood. The present study integrates hydrological modelling with ecological and socio-economic datasets to manage SIF productivity under changing regimes. This interdisciplinary approach links river discharge, inundation duration, sediment flux, and thermal variability to critical life-cycle stages such as spawning, nursery development, and feeding. The integration of fisher observations and traditional ecological knowledge enhances policy relevance of the findings. Scenario-based modelling evaluates how climate change and infrastructure operations influence SIF yield, biodiversity, and livelihoods. By linking hydrological models with SIF productivity this study demonstrates the critical pathway for transforming vulnerability into viability ensuring that small indigenous fisheries remain resilient, productive, and central to the food and nutritional security of millions in the Ganga Basin.

Keywords Small Indigenous Fisheries • Ganga River Basin • Hydrological dynamics • Climate change • Fisheries productivity • Vulnerability to viability

1. Introduction

Inland fisheries provide a wide range of societal benefits (Arthur et al., 2015), including ensuring food security for millions of rural households and creating employment opportunities in developing countries (FAO, 2015; Youn et al., 2014). As a result, Small Indigenous Fishes (SIFs) are frequently consumed by most rural communities (Roos et al., 2007). SIFs are those species that measure up to 25 cm of maturity in their life cycle (Karnatak et al., 2024; Ray et al., 2023; Islam et al., 2023; Rahman et al., 2022; Duarah et al., 2019; Hossain et al., 1999). Based on the assessment completed by NBFGR, of the approximately 450 SIFs in India, about 23% (104 species) are highly important for their role in the aquarium trade and for providing local livelihood (Samal et al., 2024; Ekka et al., 2024). The maximum diversity of SIFs has been recorded from the Northeast region (Bayen et al., 2022).

In many parts of India, the concept of 'trash fish' is rarely mentioned or applied. All non-poisonous fish, especially SIFs, have assured market demand and fetch high prices, typically ranging from INR 300 to INR 600 (US\$7-14) per kg (Mohapatra et al., 2018; Kumar, 2010). The fisherfolk traditionally harvest SIFs from rivers, canals, wetlands, and floodplains. SIFs are prolific breeders, require minimal management, and

thrive in both lentic and lotic ecosystems. Studies indicate that the ability of self-recruiting species (SRS) to sustain themselves in both natural and controlled environments is crucial for the livelihood security of rural households and communities (Islam et al., 2023; Sarkar et al., 2020; Mohanty et al., 2013; Majumder & Lorenzen, 1999).

SIFs of freshwater origin serve not only as a vital source of protein for rural households but also provide essential micronutrients such as calcium, zinc, iron, and fatty acids (Halwart, 2008). Kongsback et al. (2008) stated that SIFs provide better nutrition since they are generally eaten as a whole. Traditional community fishing has been sustained by SIFs, which are available all year round, and provide income to small-scale fishers. Therefore, SIFs are increasingly being recognised as highly valuable resources from economic, livelihood, nutritional, and environmental perspectives.

The River Ganga is a primary source of diverse fish, including small native species (Tripathi et al., 2017). It provides an easily accessible source of animal protein for human consumption, supplies six critical but often deficient micronutrients and maintains the livelihoods of fishers living across the Ganga River stretch (Stevens et al., 2022; White et al., 2021; Hanif et al., 2016). The River Ganga has been a source of indigenous fish germplasm for decades. About 215 fish species were reported from the river Ganga, of which 64 are considered SIF species, belonging to 34 families and 14 orders across the entire Ganga River stretch. The order Cypriniformes (36%) was found to be the most dominant in the SIF fish group, followed by Siluriformes (16%) and Clupeiformes (11%). The abundance of the indigenous fish species in the river Ganga showed the maximum contribution of SIFs (Ray et al., 2023). Currently, SIFs are considered the major catch of the River Ganga, besides large fish, and they significantly contribute to the overall fish landing (Das et al., 2023).

Aquatic biodiversity is stressed throughout the world, and SIFs are no exception. About 39% of all freshwater species of aquatic ecosystems are currently extinct, endangered, or vulnerable worldwide (Gatti, 2016; Hanif et al., 2016). In India and other Asian countries, SIFs are primarily exploited as a part of capture fisheries (Sarkar & Lakra, 2010; Baishya et al., 2016). Fishes generally face a threatened condition owing to habitat degradation, mortality, indiscriminate catch, unsuccessful breeding due to pollution, predation, presence of chemicals in water sources and environmental change (Hanif et al., 2016). Das et al. (2023) reported that SIFs like *J. coitor*, *S. bacaila*, and *G. chapra* are being exploited below their optimum exploitation levels and using small mesh mosquito nets is one of the primary causes of massive loss of juvenile fish and brooders in the river. Considering the multifunctional roles of SIFs in food security, livelihood and biological control, their conservation and sustainable management are of critical importance (Saha et al., 2018).

Small-scale fisheries (SSF) support the livelihoods of over 90% of the world's 120 million capture fishers and are crucial for food security and poverty alleviation (V2V Global Partnership, 2021). Within the Ganga basin, SIFs represent a vital component of SSF. SIFs of the Ganga basin sustain the livelihoods, nutrition, and cultural identity of thousands of riverine communities. These communities are economically marginalised and increasingly vulnerable to both environmental and institutional changes, yet they also hold inherent strengths and resilience. Therefore, transitioning from vulnerability to viability is urgent to secure the livelihoods, ecological health, and social well-being of these communities.

Against this backdrop, the recent workshop on “*Inland Small-Scale Fisheries in the Ganga River Basin: Transitioning from Vulnerability to Viability*” provided an important platform for stakeholders to discuss challenges, identify what is already working, and develop strategies and pathways for transition. This reflective paper draws on those discussions to highlight key issues, document shared insights, and explore possible directions for strengthening small indigenous fisheries in the Ganga basin, aiming to chart pathways from Vulnerability to Viability (V2V).

2. Methodology

This reflective paper employs a Situational Analysis Framework to understand the vulnerabilities and potential pathways for transitioning Small Indigenous Fisheries (SIFs) of the Ganga Basin from Vulnerability to Viability (V2V). A participatory consensus workshop served as the primary research tool, integrating the Consensus Workshop Method with elements of the Nominal Group Technique (NGT). This approach helped participants to move from individual reflections to collective synthesis, co-producing knowledge grounded in lived experiences, field realities, and scholarly insights. The focus was on generating policy-relevant and community-informed solutions rather than quantitative models.

Participants were purposively selected to represent the entire SIF value chain and governance spectrum, including small-scale fishers (men and women), traders, members of women's self-help groups, community-based organisations, fisheries officials, and researchers. Selection was based on direct engagement in SIF harvesting, marketing, or governance, representation across key Ganga Basin districts, and willingness to engage in collaborative problem-solving. This ensured the inclusion of marginalised voices, such as landless fishers and women collectors, while also capturing perspectives from governance and market actors.

The workshop followed a structured sequence: it began with a plenary framing session to establish a shared understanding of SIF ecology, market dynamics, and institutional challenges. Participants then individually listed challenges and solutions, which were clustered into thematic categories within small mixed groups into thematic categories, and mapped for causal relationships. Finally, groups presented their findings in a plenary session, followed by synthesis and prioritisation of key issues and solutions. All workshop materials, including cards, flipcharts, and causal maps, were photographed and archived. Plenary and group discussions were audio-recorded with consent and later transcribed. Two note-takers documented facilitation dynamics and non-verbal cues. Data analysis was guided by the V2V framework, focusing on two dimensions: (a) Drivers of vulnerability, such as ecological, socio-economic, and governance stressors; and (b) Enablers of viability, including resilience strategies and institutional supports. The analysis identified salient drivers, mapped causal linkages through visual 'causal trees', and summarised proposed solutions aligned with V2V principles by the participants. Findings were synthesised under three thematic areas:

- (1) Current vulnerabilities of SIFs in the Ganga Basin
- (2) Existing viable practices and adaptive strategies among fishing communities
- (3) Key enablers and pathways to strengthen the transition from Vulnerability to Viability

To prioritise enablers for the transition of SIFs from vulnerability to viability, a form of Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) technique was applied. Three criteria: Impact, Feasibility, and Equity were assigned weights of 0.5, 0.3, and 0.2, respectively, based on literature review and expert judgment. Each enabler was rated on a 1–5 scale under these criteria, and a composite weighted score was computed to determine their relative importance, using the following weighted formula

$$\text{Weighted Score} = (\text{Impact} \times 0.5) + (\text{Feasibility} \times 0.3) + (\text{Equity} \times 0.2)$$

To ensure credibility, workshop findings were triangulated with secondary literature, official statistics, and field observations. A summary of key results was shared with participants for validation through a single-round, Delphi-style feedback process. Ethical standards were strictly upheld throughout stakeholder engagement.

Figure 1

Schematic representation of participatory and analytical workflow

3. Key reflections

3.1 SIF production trends (2016 - 2024) across major landing centres of the Ganga

Figure 2.

Temporal trends in SIF production across the middle stretch of the River Ganga (2016 - 2024)

Source: NMCG annual report year 2024

The time-series (2016 - 2024) of SIFs production across different stretches of the River Ganga (Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, West Bengal) shows clear heterogeneity: Narora, Prayagraj, Bhagalpur, and Patna are among the highest-contributing landing centres and consistently recorded high production (>55%) over the years. Across the region, SIFs are frequently taken as bycatch in small-mesh gears (set bag nets, push nets and fine-mesh gillnets), which increases incidental removals of juveniles and non-target taxa and can alter population structure over time (Sarkar et al., 2021). Studies report that operational mesh sizes in inland fisheries vary widely but are concentrated in the small-mesh (roughly 5 - 30 mm inter-bar) in both wetlands and riverine systems (Kumar et al., 2022).

Where species have high local demand, fishers deliberately target them using appropriately sized gillnets: for example, *Cabdio morar* is heavily exploited in parts of UP and Bihar and is commonly caught with fine gillnets with nominal mesh sizes reported around 20–22 mm in targeted fishing (Baitha et al., 2018). While in parts of West Bengal, the river shad (*Gudusia chapra*) is taken with slightly larger meshes, and studies report the use of nets in the ~20–35 mm class, depending on local preference and size structure (Kumar et al., 2024). Gear selectivity therefore plays a major role in shaping catch composition and bycatch rates.

Species such as *Corica soborna*, *Cabdio morar*, *Johnius coitor*, *Gudusia chapra*, *Mystus cavasius*, *Notopterus notopterus*, *Ompok bimaculatus*, *M. tengara*, *M. gulio*, *Setipinna phasa*, *Ompok pabda*, and *Amblypharyngodon mola* are highly preferred across these regions and command strong market demand due to their delicate texture, taste, and nutritional richness (Sinha et al., 2024). These fish are integral to household food security and are often sold fresh for immediate consumption.

Figure 3

Common Small Indigenous Fish Species of the Gangetic Basin

Source: ICAR - CFRI Annual Report 2024; Fish base

3.2 Nutritional and therapeutic values of SIFs

SIFs offer higher nutritional value because it is more common for humans to ingest the entire fish, including the head, bones, and eyes, thus utilising all available nutrients and micronutrients (Kongsback et al., 2008; Mohanty et al., 2019). These fish are also rich sources of proteins, fatty acids, minerals, and vitamins. They consist of 2 – 12% lipids, 20 – 30% protein, and about 70 – 80% moisture (Roos & Islam, 2003). SIFs, which are often overlooked in aquaculture, such as *Amblypharyngodon mola*, *Puntius sophore*, *Anabas testudineus*, etc., have comparable or even higher protein content than the IMCs (>16%) (Mohanty et al., 2019). Recent studies on amino acid composition analysis of SIFs of River Ganga revealed that the SIFs (*Eleotris fusca*, *Gagata cenia*, *Apocryptes bato*, *Acanthocobitis botia*, *Securicula gora*) are a rich source of essential amino acids like glycine, glutamic acid, cysteine, threonine, methionine, phenylalanine, lysine, isoleucine, leucine, histidine, and valine (Das et al., 2024).

SIFs are also rich in heart-friendly omega-3 fatty acids like docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) and Eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA), and commonly consumed SIFs like *Amblypharyngodon mola*, *Puntius sophore*, and *Gudusia chapra* are among the Omega-3-rich fish species (Mohanty et al., 2016). Mineral composition analysis shows that SIFs are excellent sources of essential micronutrients, especially calcium, iron, and zinc in *Xenentodon cancila*, *Gudusia chapra*, *Amblypharyngodon mola*, *Puntius sophore*, *Ailia coila* (Mohanty et al., 2016). They are also rich in vitamins, particularly vitamins A, D and E, as well as vitamins B1, B2 and B3. Some commonly consumed, small freshwater fish species like *Amblypharyngodon mola*, *Parambassis ranga*, *Osteobrama cotio* and *Esomus danricus* have been found to contain high amounts of preformed Vitamin A in the form of retinol and 3, 4-dehydroretinol isomers, which are easily digestible by the human gut and can significantly contribute to meeting the nutritional needs of rural communities (Mohanty, 2013; Islam, 2023).

SIFs provide better calcium bioavailability than milk, making them a valuable supplement for expectant and lactating mothers (Bogard et al., 2015; Saha et al., 2024). Moreover, one kilogram of SIFs contains a vitamins and minerals equivalent to about fifty kilograms of large fish, such as Indian Major carp (Mohanty et al., 2013). These small fish provide great nutritional and therapeutic value (Table 1). SIFs are rich in omega-3 fatty acids that improve maternal and child health, boost immunity, and support growth (Khanjani et al., 2024; Saha et al., 2024). Regular intake of SIFs thus helps prevent chronic diseases such as heart ailments, diabetes, arthritis, depression, and asthma. Thus, SIFs serve as ‘nutrition-sensitive fisheries,’ aligning with India’s National Nutrition Mission goals.

3.3 Cultural significance of SIFs

Fish is not merely valued as a nutritious food rich in omega-3 fatty acids and proteins; it holds far deeper significance for communities along the Ganga basin. Beyond being food, fish are embedded in rituals, traditions, and everyday practices, symbolising prosperity, fertility, and abundance, thereby becoming inseparable from cultural and religious customs (Chakraborty, 2024).

India, with its ancient civilisations and diverse religions, has long regarded fish as sacred and auspicious. They are celebrated as protectors, harbingers of good fortune, and emblems of beauty and purity (Gupta et al., 2016). Folklore, oral traditions, literature, astrology, and regional myths all reflect the deep cultural imprint of fish.

In Bengal, for instance, fish is considered highly propitious and is often consumed before beginning a new journey or on an important occasion. It also remains a centrepiece in local festivities and communal events. The cultural impact of fish has been seen on a large scale that cannot be treated separately. This deep-rooted connection supports stable markets and strengthens livelihood security for small-scale fishers.

Table 1	
<i>Nutritional Significance of Small Indigenous Fish Species</i>	
Small Indigenous Fish	Nutritional Importance
<i>Clarias batrachus</i> (Magur)	Rich in protein, iron, recommended for pregnant women for strength and recovery (Paul et al., 2015).
<i>Channa punctatus</i> (Spotted snakehead murrel)	High protein and fatty acids help in ameliorating wound lesions, post-parturition, and various skin diseases (Zehra et al., 2024).
<i>Ompok pabda</i> (Pabda)	High-quality protein; supports maternal and general health (Hossain et al., 2024).
<i>Puntius spp.</i> (Punti)	Affordable protein source; improves calcium and micronutrient intake (Roos et al., 2002; Mohanty et al., 2019).
<i>Amblypharyngodon mola</i> (Mola)	Rich in vitamin A; prevents night blindness; eaten whole for maximum mineral absorption (Goswami et al., 2019).
<i>Channa gachua</i> (Snakehead murrel)	Boosts energy; aids recovery from anaemia, asthma, and body pain (Paray et al., 2025).
<i>Salmophasia bacaila</i> (Chela)	High calcium content supports lactating mothers (Islam et al., 2023).
<i>Chela cachius</i> (Chela)	Source of protein and micronutrients; contributes to dietary diversity (Saha et al., 2024).
<i>Esomus danricus</i> (Darkina)	Rich in minerals; accessible to low-income households (Das et al., 2024).
<i>Puntius sophore</i> (Sophe)	Improves calcium and micronutrient intake; affordable (Goswami et al., 2019).
<i>Mystus tengara</i> (Tengra)	Protein-rich; used in traditional remedies for strength (Ahmed et al., 2022).
<i>Gudusia chapra</i> (Chapila)	Affordable source of vitamins and minerals; aids conception (Thilsted et al., 2013).

3.4 IUCN status

A total of 215 fish species representing 19 orders and 132 genera were recorded from the Ganga, of which 18 species belonging to 8 orders and 12 families were reported under the IUCN Red-list. The maximum threatened fish species (Table 3) were found in the middle stretch of the River Ganga, viz. Buxar, Patna, Bhagalpur, Farakka, Berhampore and Balagrah, followed by the upper stretch, viz. Bijour and Narora. The Ganga River harbours a rich diversity of flora and fauna, including 215 fish species belonging to 19 orders and 132 genera (Das et al., 2023). Among these, 18 species from 8 orders and 12 families are listed under the IUCN Red List, making their conservation a matter of concern (Ray et al., 2023). The highest number of threatened fish species has been reported from the Middle Stretch of the river, covering Buxar, Patna, Bhagalpur, Farakka, Berhampore, and Balagarh, followed by the Upper Stretch at Bijour and Narora (Swain et al., 2021). SIFs such as *Ompok bimaculatus*, *Ompok pabda*, *Ailia coila*, and *Parambassis lala* are categorised as Near Threatened (NT) in the Ganga, according to the IUCN Red List. Their populations are declining mainly due to dam construction, land-use changes, water pollution, industrial discharge, and illegal fishing, all of which are altering fish diversity in the basin (Swain et al., 2021; Mishra et al., 2011).

3.5 Indigenous Traditional Knowledge (ITK)

Fishers possess rich traditional knowledge about fisheries and fishing skills, which they have gathered from their experiences and passed down across generations. Indigenous knowledge may be locally developed or generated elsewhere (Van Der Bleik & Van Veldhuisen, 1993). Such Indigenous Traditional Knowledge (ITK) is socially desirable, economically affordable, sustainable, involves minimal risk, and focuses on the efficient utilisation of eco-friendly resources (Ponnusamy *et al.*, 2009; Shenoy, 2009).

Fishers in the Ganga basin continue to rely on several ITKs practices for catching and managing SIFs. They use bamboo traps like Chero, Chokhia, Atal, and Banki to harvest fish from slow-flowing water channels and marshes. Traditional pot techniques (hundi') baited with leftover food are used in shallow waters to catch air-breathing SIFs. Certain SIFs also hold therapeutic and nutritional value, such as *Channa gachua*, believed to boost energy and fight anaemia, while *Salmophasia bacaila*, recommended lactating mothers for enhancing milk production (Roy *et al.*, 2020). Preservation and transportation techniques, like adding lemon juice to water for live *Anabas*, have been validated by ICAR-CIFRI. Similarly, extract from unripe gaab (*Diospyros embryopteris*) fruit is used for strengthening fishing nets (Roy *et al.*, 2020).

Fishers also use a variety of traditional gears such as Ghunji (for catching bottom-dwelling fishes like *Trichogaster chuna* and *Anabas testudineus*, Palu'i (for catching fishes in slimy or muddy areas), Dughare (for catching SIFs in shallow waters), Baṛasi (for small and medium-sized fishes), Cap Jal and Drag net. Other commonly used gears include Ghun Jal, Phammdi, Wheel chip, Jhim chip, Togi, Jaṭa, Laṛka, and Kemmca, which are locally adapted for targeting SIFs in different aquatic habitats (Mohapatra *et al.*, 2018). These types of ITKs reflect the deep-rooted traditional knowledge of Ganga fishers in conserving and utilising SIFs for livelihood, health, and resilience. Integrating validated ITKs into co-management plans can effectively bridge traditional wisdom and modern conservation practices.

Figure 4

Various woven bamboo traps used to catch SIFs

4. Key drivers of vulnerability

Vulnerability is understood as a function of exposure, sensitivity, and the capacity to respond to diverse drivers of change. It is not merely about being exposed to risks but also encompasses how sensitive a system is to those risks and how effectively it can respond or adapt (Dias et al., 2023).

4.1 Environmental/Biophysical drivers

Pollution in the Ganga from industrial effluents, untreated sewage, and agricultural runoff continues to deteriorate water quality and impact fish stocks (Tiwari et al., 2022). Heavy metals such as arsenic, chromium, nickel, and lead are reported at levels that remain problematic (Matta et al., 2023). Changes in flow, water depth, temperature, and substrate composition caused by barrages, mining, and other habitat modifications have reduced the suitability of breeding grounds and nursery habitats of SIFs (Kamboj et al., 2022). Many SIFs, such as *Salmostoma bacaila*, have two recruitment peaks per year, and disturbances like pollution or habitat loss during these periods can severely constrain population recovery (Ray et al., 2023).

Rainfall variability has also emerged as a key stressor. Delays or changes in rainfall magnitude strongly influence gonadal maturation and spawning phenology in native catfishes, showing how altered rainfall can contribute to breeding failure or shifts in timing (Sarkar et al., 2019). Large dams and barrages, particularly Farakka, have diverted much of the dry-season flow, reducing downstream discharge, shifting the estuarine zone, and altering fish-fauna composition (Das, 2024; Mazumder, 2023; Chakraborty, 2021). Reduced river flows, over-abstraction of groundwater and an expanding irrigation networks, lower tributary discharge and the river's dilution capacity, raising pollutant concentrations and disrupting natural spawning cues (Dutta, 2020).

Heavy silt loads and catchment degradation have changed river morphology, reducing nursery areas for sediment-adapted species (Raff et al., 2023). Altered turbidity and flow regimes from dam operations also disrupt the sediment and light conditions that many fishes use as spawning and feeding signals (Chen et al., 2023). Industrial and municipal contamination further aggravates the problem: studies document Pb, Cd, Cr, Cu, and Zn in Ganga sediments and fish tissue, while nearly three-quarters of sewage generated in the basin still enters untreated (Mohammad, 2016). In Uttar Pradesh alone, about 3,513 MLD of wastewater from untapped drains is discharged into the Ganga and its tributaries, directly affecting fish diversity (Mourya et al., 2019; Kumar et al., 2024).

Mining in the Uttarakhand stretches of the Ganga has disturbed turbidity, water depth, and velocity (Kamboj et al., 2021). Comparative studies between mining and non-mining sites show significantly lower fish diversity, both in species richness and abundance, in mining-impacted zones (Kamboj et al., 2023). Riverbank erosion caused by mining also reduces breeding and nursery grounds of SIFs. Hydrological alterations from dams, barrages, and hydropower projects destroy breeding habitats across the basin. Projects in the Alaknanda and Bhagirathi, along with barrages like Bijnor, Narora, and Kanpur, continue to influence ecological flows and food resources (Kumar et al., 2022; Raj et al., 2024). In addition, climate stress is increasingly evident: rising temperatures, erratic rainfall, and flooding events are altering breeding seasons and further threatening the persistence of SIFs.

4.2 Socio-economic drivers

The livelihoods of SSFs in the Ganga are deeply entwined with fishery resources, especially SIFs, but socio-economic conditions intensify their vulnerability. Fishing remains the primary income source for a large majority of households. In some stretches, such as Bhagirathi–Hooghly, up to 88.6% of fisher households rely on fishing as their primary occupation, contributing about 70% of total family income (Pandit et al.,

2019). Dependence on fisheries is generational: communities like Jele/Malo have fished for decades, and reductions in catch have triggered migration and loss of interest among youth (Dey et al., 2020).

The capacity of these communities to absorb such shocks remains weak, leading them to depend on SIFs for year-round availability. Studies show that most SIFs in the lower Ganga are at or near full exploitation (e.g., *Cabdio morar*, *Salmastoma bacaila*, *Gudusia chapra*); some are overexploited (Ray et al., 2023). In such contexts, fishers are often compelled to increase effort or exploit small indigenous fishes (SIFs) more intensively, even during breeding seasons. Limited education and skills among fishers reduce their ability to adopt alternative livelihoods or sustainable practices, while financial pressures and debt tied to fishing compel them to overexploit resources, adding to their vulnerability (Pandit et al., 2020). With limited alternatives, pressure to catch more, and little control over the market, fishers are caught in a cycle of vulnerability that threatens both their livelihoods and the small fish populations they depend on.

4.3 Governance and policy drivers

With limited enforcement preventing illegal fishing or the indiscriminate use of small-mesh nets that catch juveniles, there is a loss of juvenile fish and brooders, significantly reducing future fish stocks (Ray et al., 2023). Sarkar (2015) highlighted that the lack of clear ownership and management rights over fishing areas contributes to the depletion of fish stocks and undermines conservation efforts.

Existing regulations, such as gear restrictions and seasonal fishing bans, are often poorly enforced. This enforcement gap allows for destructive fishing practices, including small-mesh nets that indiscriminately capture juvenile fish, thereby hindering stock regeneration. Ray et al. (2023) confirmed that such practices significantly reduce future fish stocks in the Ganga River. The construction of dams, barrages, and other infrastructure projects has also altered the natural flow of the Ganga River, adversely affecting the ichthyofaunal diversity of the river (Das et al., 2023).

Institutional and policy access is weak, as many traditional caste-based fishing communities, including Mallah, Nishad, or Bind, remain outside formal fisher registration and cooperatives, missing out on government schemes like Matsya Sampada Yojana (Dey et al., 2020). The National Mission for Clean Ganga (NMCG) has emphasized the need for comprehensive governance reforms to address pollution, overfishing, and habitat degradation in the Ganga River system.

4.4 Social & demographic drivers

The river Ganga spans 3,795 fishing villages across five states and 47 districts (Badola et al., 2024). High population pressure in the Ganga basin increases demand for fish, pressures on river resources, and intensifies competition among fishers (Kelkar et al., 2021). Millions of people live along the river, use its water, pollute it, and rely on fish for food or income. Women are typically more involved in post-harvest work, but are undervalued, have less access to decision-making, and receive smaller shares of income; their labour is often invisible in studies (Mahmud et al., 2025; Rao et al., 2024; Kimani et al., 2022; Cole et al., 2018). Many Ganga fishers belong to socially or economically marginalised communities (low caste, minority, etc.), with a weak political voice, restricted access to resources, and often living in flood-prone or erosion-prone riparian zones (Bhattacharya et al., 2024). This reduces their ability to influence policy or protect their own interest. Traditional fishing communities have a deep cultural connection to the Ganga River. These communities possess remarkable ecological knowledge about rivers, SIFs, and biodiversity. However, with the degradation of fisheries throughout the Gangetic plains, traditional knowledge and practices are eroding.

Figure 5

Schematic representations of Key Drivers of Vulnerability

4.5 Exposure to shocks & stressors

Fishers in the Ganga basin are exposed to multiple overlapping shocks that severely affect both fish stocks and their livelihoods (Sharma et al., 2019). Hydrological extremes, including unpredictable rainfall, erratic dry and flood seasons, and weak flood pulses, disrupt ecological cues essential for breeding, impair floodplain connectivity, and reduce overall productivity (Islam et al., 2021; Sharma et al., 2019). In the Bhagalpur/Kahalgao region, fishers report sharp declines in yield during years of poor flooding, increasing competition, while strong flood pulses provide temporary relief and access to richer habitats (Kelkar et al., 2022). Market shocks and price fluctuations, especially when supply is low or during closed seasons, severely affect incomes (Khandekar et al., 2019). Fishers, depending on SIFs, have limited savings or coping mechanisms. Policy shocks, such as sudden restrictions like bans on fishing gear or closed seasons, can cause distress among small-scale fishers who rely on SIF catches for income.

5. Resilience and adaptive practices

Vulnerability is defined as a function of exposure, sensitivity, and the capacity to respond to diverse drivers of change. By These vulnerabilities can be addressed through inclusive governance, capacity building, and adaptive strategies (Sall & Sow, 2025).

5.1 Current viabilities

SIFs play a vital role in ensuring nutritional and economic security for marginalised communities. They remain a rich and affordable source of protein, supported by growing awareness of their nutritional importance (Das et al., 2024). Economically, regular access to local markets and small-scale household trade offers steady, though modest, income streams for fisher families. The cultural embeddedness of

fishing, linked to rituals, festivals, and community identity, ensures its continuity through intergenerational knowledge transfer (Gupta et al., 2015). Moreover, growing domestic and export demand for ornamental SIFs, along with breeding programmes in states like West Bengal, highlights their expanding market potential (Sinha et al., 2024). Biologically, the auto-recruiting nature of many SIF species enhances resilience to ecological and supply chain disruptions. These species require no feed, fertiliser or pesticide inputs or the consumptive use of fresh water (Karnatak et al., 2022), making them environmentally sustainable.

5.2 Adaptive practices

Fishers exhibit diverse adaptive strategies to sustain their livelihoods under changing environmental and socio-economic conditions. These include modifying gears, timings, and fishing grounds according to seasonal river fluctuations and diversifying their livelihoods by integrating fishing with farming and wage labour. ITKs continues to guide sustainable harvesting practices for SIFs, while women play crucial roles in post-harvest processing and alternative income generation (Bhattacharya et al., 2024). Community-led governance, through fisher cooperatives and informal rules further strengthens collective management and income security (Roy et al., 2022). Additionally, ecological assessments and GIS-based monitoring in the Ganga basin indicate increasing use of scientific tools to support sustainable resource management and data-driven decision-making. These adaptive practices exemplify community-led transitions aligning with the V2V framework's pillars of Agency, Assets, and Access.

Figure 6

Current viabilities and adaptive practices among SIF Fishers

Recent regionally focused studies and reviews from the lower Gangetic wetlands have highlighted that SIFs produced in floodplain wetlands are a regular and affordable source of nutrition and income for fisher families. A significant portion of SIFs consumed in fisher households comes from their own harvests, which reduces household food costs and improves dietary diversity (Lianthumluaia et al., 2024; Roy et al., 2025). These local studies form an empirical basis for V2V approaches that aim to protect wetlands and community access.

5.3 Responses to existing vulnerabilities for SIFs to strengthen the transition

To systematically evaluate and prioritise the key enablers that can facilitate the transition of Small Indigenous Fisheries (SIFs) from vulnerability to viability, a structured decision-support approach was employed using a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) technique, which allows the integration of both qualitative and quantitative judgments, drawing on stakeholder consultations, focus group discussions, and relevant literature. Three main criteria were selected to assess each enabler:

- (i) **Impact potential** – the extent to which an enabler contributes to ecological sustainability, nutritional security, and livelihood improvement
- (ii) **Feasibility** – the practicality of implementing the enabler, considering institutional capacity, cost, and local acceptance
- (iii) **Equity and inclusion** – the degree to which the enabler promotes gender equality, social inclusion, and fair access to benefits

Each enabler was rated on a **five-point scale** (1 = low, 5 = high), based on qualitative assessments and expert judgement. A weighted average method was used to calculate composite scores, assigning weights of 0.4 to impact, 0.3 to feasibility, and 0.3 to equity.

Rank	Enabler	Impact	Feasibility	Equity	Score	How It Helps
1	Community-Centred Governance and Institutions	5	4	5	4.7	Ensures fisher participation, leverages local knowledge, and forms the foundation for all other interventions
2	Policy & Regulatory Support	5	4	4	4.5	Secure access, regulations, and legal recognition protect fish stocks and livelihoods
3	Ecological & Environmental Restoration and Health	5	3	4	4.3	Habitat restoration, water quality improvement, and protection of spawning grounds directly increase SIF abundance
4	Gender Inclusion / Women Empowerment	4	4	5	4.3	Women's involvement in the value chain enhances equity and community resilience

5	Adaptive Capacity / Livelihood Diversification	4	4	4	4.0	Alternative livelihoods & coping strategies reduce vulnerability during lean seasons and environmental shocks
6	Value Chain Improvements & Market Linkages	4	4	3	3.9	Improved infrastructure, market access, and reduced intermediaries increase economic viability
7	Identification and Assessment of SIFs, including nutrient profiling	4	3	3	3.7	Provides baseline data for conservation and planning, and insights into nutritionally and economically important fish species
8	Integrated & Ecosystem-Based Management Approaches	5	2	3	3.7	Holistic management addresses multiple stressors and ensures long-term sustainability
9	Awareness and Education on Overfishing / Fishing Effort Regulations	3	4	3	3.4	Promotes sustainable practices and compliance with regulations
10	Use of Technology / ICTs	4	3	3	3.4	Supports traceability, early warning, and communication
11	Vulnerability Assessment and Spatial Distribution	4	3	2	3.4	Helps identify priority zones and plan interventions
12	Climate-Resilient Technology	4	2	3	3.2	Prepares fisheries and fishers for climate shocks for the longer term
13	Ranching of SIFs to Increase Native Stock	4	2	2	3.0	Boosts native fish populations and biodiversity
14	Study-Based Impact of Climate Change	3	3	2	2.9	Informs adaptive management and policy but has a limited immediate impact.

The ranking reveals that social and governance interventions are the highest-priority enablers for strengthening SIF resilience in the Ganga Basin. Community-led governance, supportive policies, and gender-inclusive approaches form the foundation for effective resource management by addressing structural vulnerabilities and promoting equity, participation, and adaptive capacity. These measures directly contribute to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 1 (No Poverty), 2 (Zero Hunger), 5 (Gender Equality), and 14 (Life Below Water). Prioritization highlights governance, policy, and gender inclusion as cross-cutting catalysts for viability.

Livelihood diversification and value chain improvements are medium priority enablers, providing crucial support to enhance fish stock recovery, economic viability, and nutrition security. Meanwhile, interventions such as awareness campaigns, monitoring systems, and pollution management strengthen the effectiveness of high-priority interventions by ensuring sustainable practices and environmental health.

Supporting long-term priorities, such as climate-resilient technologies, SIF assessment, and ranching, is essential for sustaining biodiversity and adapting to climate change. However, their success relies on robust governance structures, active community participation, and ecological foundations. Overall, this prioritisation indicates that governance and policy measures should be implemented first, followed by complementary ecological, economic, and technological interventions to ensure a resilient, equitable, and sustainable SIF sector. The following figure presents stakeholder reflections from a group discussion. The chart captures their lived experiences, observations, and suggestions on the key challenges and enablers for sustaining SIFs in the Ganga Basin, complementing insights drawn from the literature.

Figure 7

Response of different stakeholders on SIF resilience in the river Ganga

6. Adaptive capacity limitations

Many fisher households along the Ganga River depend primarily on SIFs. However, their adaptive capacity, the ability to cope with or recover from ecological, climatic, or socio-economic stress, is severely constrained by interrelated limitations. Low income and a lack of savings prevent fishers from investing in improved gears or alternative livelihood options. Dependence on local moneylenders charging high-interest rates further weakens financial resilience, forcing many fishers to operate in shallow-water areas with low yields (Pandit et al., 2019).

Moreover, fishers often lack the skills and resources to shift to other livelihood options. Knowledge and skill gaps exacerbate this vulnerability, as reliance on traditional ecological knowledge becomes less effective under changing river regimes (Sharma et al., 2015). Market constraints further compound their challenges. Reliance on local traders and middlemen keeps prices low, while social and educational limitations, including low literacy and caste-based marginalisation, restrict access to training, alternative employment, and government programs, leaving women and youth with few livelihood options (Hossen, 2024). Weak community institutions also hinder collective adaptation, limiting the ability to negotiate for habitat protection, pollution control, or regulated fishing rights. Collectively, these interlinked financial, ecological, social, and institutional challenges severely constrain the adaptive capacity of fishers dependent on SIF (Msomphora, 2018).

7. Case study on consumer preferences and market price variation of SIF

Small Indigenous Fish Species (SIFs) constitute an essential component of local diets, nutrition, and livelihoods across the Ganga River Basin. However, their market value and consumer demand vary widely between regions, influenced by socio-cultural preferences, awareness of nutritional importance, and local market systems. To understand these variations and understand how consumer perception influences pricing, a comparative case study was conducted in three primary states: Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, and West Bengal.

7.1 Method and rationale

The study aimed to examine how consumer preferences, awareness, and regional market conditions influence the pricing and demand of SIFs. A qualitative descriptive approach was adopted, combining field visits, price observations, and semi-structured interviews. Between May and June 2024, data were collected from nine local fish markets, three from each state: Allahabad, Ballia, and Varanasi (Uttar Pradesh); Hajipur, Bhagalpur, and Patna (Bihar); Farakka, Diamond Harbour and *Fraserganj* (West Bengal). A total of 36 retailers (12 from each market) were interviewed to gather insights.

For this case study, 10 commercially important SIFs frequently consumed by local populations were selected to represent the inland fish diet:

Mystus tengara, *M. vittatus*, *M. cavassius*, *A. coila*, *Notopterus sp.*, *Ompok pabda*, *Heteropneustes fossilis*, *Gudusia chapra*, *Amblypharyngodon mola*, *Cabdio morar*

Additionally, a few estuarine SIFs:

M. gulio, *Corica soborna*, *Polynemus paradiseus*, *Escualosa thoracata*, and *Setipinna phasa* from the West Bengal estuarine region were included to capture premium species with limited availability and high demand. The interviews explored:

- Most preferred SIFs among consumers
- Price ranges and seasonal variation
- Factors affecting demand and willingness to pay

Price data was verified through direct observation and informal conversations with wholesalers and consumers.

7.2. Observations

The study revealed distinct regional differences in consumer preferences and market pricing. The following table 3 presents some commercially important SIFs found across the three states of the Ganga River Basin. Their market prices vary significantly from one state to another, mainly due to differences in consumer demand, awareness of nutritional value, and local market dynamics.

Fish Species		Price range (INR/Kg)		
Scientific name	Local name	Uttar Pradesh	Bihar	West Bengal
<i>Mystus tengara</i>	Tengra	150-300	200-250	400-500
<i>Mystus vittatus</i>	Lal Tengra	120-300	160-220	300-500
<i>Mystus cavasius</i>	Gang Tengra	150-250	150-200	300-400
<i>Ailia coila</i>	Kajuli	600-900	300-400	800-1000
<i>Notopterus notopterus</i>	Folui	300-650	400-550	400-500
<i>Ompok pabda</i>	Pabda	300-500	300-400	500-600
<i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i>	Shingi	600-1200	350-450	500-600
<i>Gudusia chapra</i>	Khoira	80-150	120-200	350-450
<i>Amblypharyngodon mola</i>	Mourala	100-200	100-150	300-350
<i>Cabdio morar</i>	Piali	100-200	150-250	80-100
<i>Mystus gulio</i>	Nuna Tengra	-	-	300-400
<i>Corica soborna</i>	Kachki	-	-	600-800
<i>Polynemus paradiseus</i>	Topse	-	-	700-800
<i>Escualosa thoracata</i>	Gang Mourala	-	-	300-400
<i>Setipinna phasa</i>	Phasa	-	-	350-400

In Uttar Pradesh, SIFs such as *Mystus tengara* are sold for ₹150–300 per kg, while in West Bengal, the same fish fetches a much higher price of ₹400–500 per kg. Similarly, *Ailia coila* and *Ompok pabda*, which are highly valued for their taste and nutritional quality, are sold at premium prices in West Bengal (₹800–1000 and ₹500–600 per kg, respectively) compared to Uttar Pradesh, where they range between ₹600–900 and ₹400–600 per kg.

Conversely, species like *Cabdio morar* show the opposite trend; it is relatively cheaper in West Bengal (₹80–100 per kg) compared to Uttar Pradesh and Bihar, reflecting regional preferences and awareness. In West Bengal, where fish is a staple food and people are more aware of the nutritional benefits of SIFs, market demand and prices are generally higher. In contrast, in Bihar and parts of Uttar Pradesh, SIFs are often caught for self-consumption rather than commercial sales, leading to lower market value. In some areas, these fish are even treated as bycatch rather than primary catch.

In estuarine stretches of the Ganga, such as Farakka, Diamond Harbour, and Fraserganj, species like *Mystus gulio*, *Polynemus paradiseus*, and *Corica soborna* fetch premium prices (₹600–800 per kg) attributed to their taste, limited availability, and strong demand in coastal markets. Overall, the difference in price across states reflects a combination of consumer awareness, cultural preference, accessibility to markets, and the nutritional reputation of each species. The study suggests that improving consumer awareness of SIF nutritional benefits could enhance value chains and fisher incomes.

Key observations:

1. **Cultural familiarity drives preference:** In states like West Bengal, where fish forms a staple diet, have stronger consumer loyalty to SIFs and more willing to pay premium prices.
2. **Nutritional awareness enhances value:** Consumers who familiar with the health benefits of small fish tend to pay more, increasing overall market value.

Harvesting practices reflect demand: In some regions with high demand, fishers use targeted gears to catch SIFs. Elsewhere, SIFs are often treated as bycatch, sold cheaply, or even given away.

Figure 8

SIF catch share percentage in river Ganga

8. Conclusions

Reflections from stakeholder discussions reveal SIFs in the Ganga Basin are far more than a source of food and income; they are woven into the cultural and social fabric of riverside communities. Despite persistent challenges such as pollution, habitat degradation, overfishing, and climate variability, the experiences shared during the workshop show that local fishers already employ adaptive strategies: adjusting fishing practices seasonally, diversifying livelihoods, and drawing on traditional knowledge to sustain their resources.

Evidence from recent studies reinforces these reflections. SIFs exhibit a degree of natural resilience through auto-recruitment, and household-level trade of SIFs provides steady, if modest, economic support. However, sustaining these fisheries into the future requires nurturing the enablers identified both in literature and by the stakeholder community-centered governance, gender inclusion, pollution management, habitat restoration, and climate-resilient practices.

The concepts of vulnerability, viability, and enabler are not standalone; they interact dynamically (Dias *et al.*, 2023). Environmental degradation and socio-economic stressors, such as increased livelihood dependence and overfishing pressure, can be mitigated by existing adaptive practices, like seasonal fishing adjustments and livelihood diversification, which help buffer these shocks. Strengthening institutional mechanisms, empowering women, and improving market linkages can amplify these existing adaptive capacities, converting vulnerability into viability (V2V). Thus, the pathways from vulnerability to viability are shaped by the interplay between ecological health, community capacity, and governance responsiveness. In essence, the pathway from Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) lies in bridging lived experiences and scientific insights: recognizing what is already working in communities while strengthening systems to support ecological and socio-economic resilience.

9. Future research needs

- **Strengthen data collection on SIFs:** There is an urgent need to improve and systematically collect data particularly concerning SIFs, at both local and national levels. Accurate data will help bring attention to their real contribution to nutrition, income, and ecological balance, which often goes unnoticed.
- **Promote cross-sectoral coordination:** To fully harness the potential of SIFs in addressing hunger and malnutrition, greater coordination is required between decision-makers in fisheries, health and nutrition, and trade sectors for better SIF-based food systems.
- **Recognise and support women and youth in the SIFs value chain:** The critical roles of women and youths in the SIFs value chain need to be more widely acknowledged and supported. Encouraging their participation through training, fair wages, and access to resources can strengthen household incomes and community well-being. This approach also contributes directly to achieving the SDGs, including SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), and SDG 5 (Gender Equality).
- **There is a need for understanding how hydrological processes (flow, water-level variability, sediment, connectivity, temperature) control productivity, recruitment and access for SIF.**

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Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) Global Partnership

The Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) project is a transdisciplinary global partnership and knowledge network. Our aim is to support the transition of small-scale fisheries (SSF) from vulnerability to viability in Africa and Asia. Vulnerability is understood as a function of exposure, sensitivity and the capacity to respond to diverse drivers of change. We use the term viability not just in its economic sense but also to include its social, political, and ecological dimensions.

The V2V partnership brings together approximately 150 people and 70 organizations across six countries in Asia (Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Thailand), six countries in Africa (Ghana, Malawi, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania), Canada and globally. This unique initiative is characterized by diverse cultural and disciplinary perspectives, extensive capacity building and graduate student training activities, and grounded case studies from two regions of the world to show how and when SSF communities can proactively respond to challenges and creatively engage in solutions that build their viability. Further information on the V2V Partnership is available here: www.v2vglobalpartnership.org.

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